

Exploring Multi-Antenna Techniques for Satellite-Terrestrial Coexistence in Upper Mid-Band

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Abstract—Future 6G communications are expected to be complemented by non-terrestrial networks (NTNs), particularly satellites, to ensure ubiquitous connectivity. Furthermore, to address the growing spectrum shortage in terrestrial networks (TNs), the upper mid-band (7-24 GHz), currently known as frequency range 3 (FR3), is emerging as a key frequency band due to its appealing balance between capacity and coverage. However, this band is already utilized by incumbent satellite communications, making the investigation of NTN and TN coexistence in FR3 critical. This paper explores linear multi-antenna receiver techniques at TN user equipment (UE), aimed at enhancing coexistence between NTN and TN, leveraging the increased number of antennas that higher frequency bands enable on UE. Specifically, we apply Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) and Interference Rejection Combining (IRC) techniques to address the dual challenges of interference suppression and signal enhancement. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of these techniques in improving TN UE performance and reducing satellite interference.

Keywords— satellites communications, non-terrestrial networks, interference mitigation, multi-antenna techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in technology, research, and standardization have positioned NTN as an integral component of future 6G communication networks [1]. Among NTNs, satellites, in particular, are considered to complement existing TNs by ensuring global coverage, including in remote and underserved regions. Furthermore, as 6G development progresses, apart from sub-6GHz and mmWave frequencies, the upper mid-band spectrum (7 – 24 GHz) is emerging as a critical frequency range for TN, owing to its potential to deliver high data rates alongside reasonable coverage [2]. This spectrum is also extensively utilized by incumbent satellite operators due to its low atmospheric attenuation, making it a prime choice for satellite communications, as evidenced by systems such as SpaceX’s Starlink [3]. The growing interest in this spectrum for both terrestrial and non-terrestrial applications highlights the need to investigate the coexistence of NTNs and TNs within these frequency ranges.

The coexistence of satellites, especially low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellites, with TNs across various frequency bands (L, S, C, Ku/Ka, Q/V-bands), has been extensively studied [4]–[8]. For instance, [4] proposes a framework to optimize the average data rates of TNs in the 28-GHz Ka-band, considering their coexistence with satellite networks and determining the optimal exclusion zone. These exclusion zones, defined around

ground stations, are areas where certain network elements are restricted from operating in the same frequency band to avoid interference. Similarly, in [5], the authors establish design criteria to protect existing satellite services from co-channel TN interference. By deriving limits on terrestrial node density and spectrum emission masks, they show that cellular networks can feasibly coexist with NTNs in the 47.2-50.2 GHz Q-band. Furthermore, [6] explores spectrum sharing between NTNs and TNs in the 2.4 GHz S-band to address potential spectrum shortages, while [7] examines spectrum sharing between 5G networks and fixed satellite services in the 3.4-4.2 GHz C-band. Moreover, [8] studies interference challenges between cellular and satellite services in the 12 GHz band and presents an ephemeris-based beamforming approach for multi-antenna base stations to protect satellite uplinks. However, conventional coexistence studies, including those focusing on centimeter bands, have primarily considered single-antenna terminals, as this represents the minimal configuration of incumbent TN users. Our study departs from this approach by examining TN UEs equipped with larger antenna arrays. The absence of incumbent TN users in this mid-band spectrum motivates our study, as it allows us to define requirements for TN UEs that can enhance coexistence with NTNs.

In this paper, we investigate a scenario involving a realistic Starlink Generation 1 (Gen1) LEO constellation and a TN, where UEs are equipped with uniform planar array (UPA) antennas. In this context, TN downlink (DL) communication in FR3 encounters co-channel interference from satellite DL transmissions. While the literature often considers cellular-to-satellite interference as the worst-case scenario [5], [7], [8], we leave this for future work and limit the scope of this paper to the satellite-to-cellular interference case, as our main focus is on understanding the implications for TN in its potential expansion into the FR3 band. Furthermore, since DL communication has a greater impact on TN end-user experience, protecting it from satellite interference is our primary concern. For this purpose, we employ the circular exclusion zone, defined by the isolation distance (radius) between TN and NTN cell centers, necessary to minimize mutual interference. Various linear multi-antenna receiver schemes, specifically MRC and IRC, as well as different antenna configurations are assessed to mitigate the interference and minimize the isolation distance between NTNs and TNs.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this work, we investigate spectrum sharing between NTN and TN in a downlink multi-satellite environment, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The NTN consists of LEO satellites, indicated by $S_k, k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, and NTN UE. A realistic dense LEO constellation, modeled after the Starlink Gen1 system [3], is implemented as shown in Fig. 2, consisting of 72 orbits (represented by cyan curves) with 22 satellites (indicated by yellow crosses) per orbit. Munich city center, given by the coordinates 48.137 N, 11.576 E, is selected as the geographical observation point to identify the visible satellites (red zone in Fig. 2), which are determined based on the minimum elevation angle, θ_{min} , seen from TN UE. Moreover, we assume that each satellite is equipped with phased array antennas that follow a radiation pattern similar to that of Starlink's direct-to-cell antennas, as depicted in Fig. 3 [9]. Additionally, we consider a single NTN user, i.e., one active NTN cell located at the edge of the exclusion zone, with satellites consistently steering their main lobe and directing all transmit power toward this cell. This assumption represents an upper bound on interference to TN UEs for several reasons. First, modern multi-beam satellites generate multiple beams to illuminate several cells, meaning the transmit power would be distributed across these beams, and not all beams would be active simultaneously, reducing the overall interference. Furthermore, placing the NTN cell at the border of the exclusion zone, the closest possible location to TN UE, maximizes potential interference. All other beams would be directed further away from the TN cell, resulting in reduced interference power.

The terrestrial gNodeB (gNB) and user terminals constitute the TN. In our study case, the TN UE is considered the victim, while the satellites in its visibility range act as interfering nodes. To protect terrestrial communication from satellite interference, a circular exclusion zone is defined around the TN with an isolation distance (radius), D_{iso} , representing the distance between the NTN and TN cell centers. Within this zone, NTN UEs shall not be served by satellites. If $D_{iso} = 0$, NTN and TN cell will coincide, and hence the satellite will interfere with the TN UE using its main lobe. However, by increasing D_{iso} , we steer the satellite's main lobe towards the NTN cell center, and thus away from the TN cell, thereby reducing its impact on the TN UE, which is now primarily affected by the satellite's side lobes (see Fig. 3).

A. Channel Model

To eliminate the interference and enhance the useful signal, the TN UE is equipped with a UPA of dimensions $N_x \times N_y$ oriented parallel to the ground. Thus, the total number of antenna elements is $N_R = N_x N_y$.

1) *Satellite Links (Satellite-to-UE)*: Assuming that satellites are in line-of-sight (LOS), we can model the channel vector between the i -th UE and k -th satellite as in [10]

$$\mathbf{h}_{k,i} = \sqrt{\frac{G_k G_R}{L_{k,i}}} \mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,i}, \phi_{k,i}), \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. System model of NTN and TN coexistence.

Fig. 2. LEO constellation.

Fig. 3. Satellite antenna pattern utilized for simulation.

$$[\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)]_{n+N_x m} = e^{j \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} (n \sin \theta_{k,i} \cos \phi_{k,i} + m \sin \theta_{k,i} \sin \phi_{k,i})}, \quad (2)$$

for $0 \leq n \leq N_x - 1$ and $0 \leq m \leq N_y - 1$. The phase term in (2) is formulated as a function of antenna array spacing d , the wavelength λ , and the signal's direction, defined by the elevation angle $\theta_{k,i}$ and azimuth angle $\phi_{k,i}$ seen from the i -th UE. The magnitude of the channel in (1) depends on the transmitter's antenna gain G_k , deduced from the radiation

pattern in Fig. 3, the receiver antenna element gain G_R , and the free space loss $L_{k,i}$. The free space loss can be formulated as

$$L_{k,i} [dB] = 20 \log_{10} r_{k,i} + 20 \log_{10} f_c + 20 \log_{10} \frac{4\pi}{c}, \quad (3)$$

where f_c represents the operating frequency, c is the speed of light and $r_{k,i}$ refers to the distance between UE i and satellite k and can be expressed in terms of elevation angle as

$$r_{k,i} = R_E \left[\sqrt{\left(\frac{h+R_E}{R_E} \right)^2 - \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_{k,i} \right)} - \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_{k,i} \right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

Here, R_E denotes the radius of the Earth, and h is the altitude of the constellation with respect to the Earth's surface. It is important to note that our simulation tool enables dynamic analysis of the constellation, accounting for satellite movements. It uses hundreds of snapshots of satellite positions, covering a wide range of elevation angles over the entire orbital period (5760 seconds).

2) *Terrestrial Links (gNB-to-UE)*: To simulate the terrestrial communication links, we utilize the QuaDRiGa (QUAsi Deterministic Radio channel GenerAtor) tool, which is well-suited for generating realistic channel models and is widely adopted in TN performance evaluations [11]–[13]. QuaDRiGa is employed to generate channel vectors for the terrestrial links under consideration, capturing both large-scale and small-scale fading effects. We use the 3GPP NR Urban Macro-Cell environment in its default configuration in QuaDRiGa, to implement the corresponding channel model as specified in 3GPP TS 38.901 [14]. This environment represents typical terrestrial base stations deployed above rooftops in densely populated urban areas, with the corresponding LOS probability dependent on distance. We simulate one gNB (T) and 10 TN UEs, randomly distributed across the TN cell according to 3GPP assumptions, and generate 100 different snapshots, resulting in 1000 unique terrestrial channel realizations for the simulation of the entire orbital period. The parameters such as frequency band, bandwidth, and antenna configurations are set according to the specifications of our study. Thus, we generate the terrestrial channel vectors for the i -th TN UE, $\mathbf{h}_{T,i}$, in the same format as the satellite channel vectors given in (1).

B. SINR and INR Models for TN UE

Since we are investigating the impact of satellite interference on terrestrial UEs, we select the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) and the Interference-to-Noise Ratio (INR), the latter commonly being used in coexistence studies, as key metrics. By utilizing the aforementioned channel vectors, the general form of the SINR and INR of the i -th TN UE can be expressed as

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{P_T \mathbf{w}_i^H \mathbf{h}_{T,i} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{w}_i}{\mathbf{w}_i^H \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{w}_i}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{INR}_i = \frac{\mathbf{w}_i^H \sum_{\forall k} P_k \mathbf{h}_{k,i} \mathbf{h}_{k,i}^H \mathbf{w}_i}{N_p \mathbf{w}_i^H \mathbf{w}_i}, \quad (6)$$

where $(\cdot)^H$ indicates the Hermitian transpose of a vector or matrix, P_T and P_k denote the transmit power of TN gNB and k -th satellite, respectively. Moreover, \mathbf{w}_i represents the equalization vector applied at receiver of the i -th TN UE and \mathbf{Z}_i is the interference-plus-noise covariance matrix excluding the own signal's contribution, defined as

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \sum_{\forall k} P_k \mathbf{h}_{k,i} \mathbf{h}_{k,i}^H + N_p \mathbf{I}. \quad (7)$$

Here, N_p represents the thermal white noise power, defined as $N_p = K_B T_{sys} B$, where T_{sys} is the receiver system's noise equivalent temperature, K_B is the Boltzmann's constant, B is the signal bandwidth and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. The system temperature can be derived as

$$T_{sys} [dBK] = N_F + 10 \log_{10} (T_0 + (T_a - T_0) 10^{-0.1N_F}), \quad (8)$$

where the term N_F represents the noise factor in dB, while T_0 and T_a are the ambient and the antenna temperature in Kelvin (K), respectively.

III. RECEIVER TECHNIQUES

A. Maximum Ratio Combiner (MRC)

MRC is a signal processing technique used to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver [15]. MRC exploits multi-antenna UPA to efficiently steer beam arrays toward the desired channel. Specifically, the beamforming weights for the received signal are chosen to be the Hermitian transpose of the desired user channel, $\mathbf{h}_{T,i}$, yielding

$$\mathbf{w}_i^H = \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H. \quad (9)$$

Hence, utilizing MRC, (5) and (6) can be rewritten as

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{P_T (\mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{h}_{T,i})^2}{\mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{h}_{T,i}}, \quad (10)$$

$$\text{INR}_i = \frac{\mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \sum_{\forall k} P_k \mathbf{h}_{k,i} \mathbf{h}_{k,i}^H \mathbf{h}_{T,i}}{N_p \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{h}_{T,i}}. \quad (11)$$

This coherent summation enhances the desired signal while minimizing the impact of noise, leading to a significantly improved SNR. However, MRC does not account for interference, it focuses solely on maximizing the desired signal's strength, making it less effective in environments with significant co-channel interference.

B. Interference Rejection Combiner (IRC)

IRC is a more advanced technique designed to enhance the desired signal while simultaneously suppressing residual interference. It accomplishes this by steering nulls toward interference sources, thereby minimizing their impact, while amplifying the desired signal. It should be noted that IRC's interference suppression capability depends on the angle of arrival of the interference signal impinging on the UPA. Since we assume the UPA at the UE is oriented parallel to the ground, interference from low elevation angles is more challenging to mitigate. However, the elevation angle for satellite communication is typically not smaller than 25° , and within

this range ($25^\circ \leq \theta_{k,i} \leq 90^\circ$), the suppression capability of IRC performs consistently well.

1) *Maximum SINR Receiver*: Maximum SINR (maxSINR) receiver is one of the suitable linear solutions for IRC. The key idea is to find the optimal weights, $\mathbf{w}_i^{\text{maxSINR}}$, that maximize (5). By applying the solution as in [16] and calculating the inverse covariance matrix, one can generate the appropriate weights as

$$\mathbf{w}_i^{\text{maxSINR}} = \alpha \mathbf{Z}_i^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}, \quad (12)$$

where α is a constant factor. Note that this factor is canceled out in (5) and (6). Hence, the achievable SINR and INR, given full channel knowledge of all interfering satellites, can be obtained by inserting (12) into (5) and (6), yielding

$$\text{SINR}_i = P_T \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{Z}_i^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{INR}_i = \frac{\mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{Z}_i^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}}{N_p \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H \mathbf{Z}_i^{-2} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}} - 1. \quad (14)$$

The maxSINR receiver thus significantly improves the SINR and INR by efficiently rejecting interference, making it particularly effective in environments with strong co-channel interference. However, this comes at the cost of higher computational complexity than MRC, due to the need for full channel knowledge of all interfering links. In practice, acquiring such comprehensive channel state information (CSI) may not always be feasible. Instead of assuming perfect CSI, the TN UE could leverage only the spatial interference direction associated with the satellite's position. Given the deterministic nature of satellite ephemeris, the maxSINR receiver could still be considered a viable technique in real-world scenarios.

2) *Minimum Mean Square Error Receiver*: An alternative IRC technique with reduced implementation complexity is the Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) receiver. This approach aims to minimize the mean square error between the transmitted signal and the received signal estimate. In scenarios where interference is uncorrelated with desired signal and treated as noise, the MMSE receiver implicitly maximizes the SINR, making it a special case of the maxSINR receiver. In fact, the autocorrelation matrix \mathbf{R}_{xx} , which contains interference, noise, and desired channels, can be readily obtained from the expected value of the outer product of the received signal vector, \mathbf{y}_i , and can be defined as

$$\mathbf{R}_{yy} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_i \mathbf{y}_i^H] = P_T \mathbf{h}_{T,i} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}^H + \sum_{\forall k} P_k \mathbf{h}_{k,i} \mathbf{h}_{k,i}^H + N_p \mathbf{I}. \quad (15)$$

Then the MMSE solution for IRC can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{w}_i^{\text{MMSE}} = \mathbf{R}_{yy}^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{T,i}. \quad (16)$$

Thus, the computational complexity primarily arises from the matrix inversion process.

As noted above, in scenarios where interference signals and noise are uncorrelated with the desired signal, maxSINR and MMSE combiners differ only by a constant factor, resulting in identical SINR/INR for both techniques. Consequently, either of the two IRC solutions can be used to obtain the SINR/INR

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS.

Parameter	Value
Carrier frequency, f_c	15 GHz
Bandwidth, B	400 MHz
Satellite altitude, h	550 km
Minimum elevation angle, θ_{min}	25°
Visible satellites on average	20
Satellite antenna gain, G_k	38 dB
Satellite EIRP	58 dBW
UE antenna element gain, G_R	-5 dB
UE noise figure, N_F	9 dB
UE antenna noise temperature, T_a	150 K
Ambient temperature, T_0	290 K
UE antenna array spacing, d	$\lambda/2$
gNB antenna array	8×8 UPA
gNB transmit power, P_T	30 dBm

expressions in (13) and (14), depending on the receiver's strategy and complexity requirements.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section provides numerical results on the performance of multi-antenna TN receivers under various system model settings given by the simulation parameters summarized in Table I. Specifically, we assess multi-antenna receivers employing MRC and IRC techniques, considering UPA antenna sizes ($N_x \times N_y$) of 4×4 and 16×16 . These sizes are selected to represent potential future antenna designs for TN UE handheld and larger devices, respectively, enabled by operation at higher frequency bands. As a baseline, we select the performance of a single-antenna receiver.

Fig. 4 displays the performance evaluation in terms of the Cumulative Distribution Functions (CDFs) of INR (left) and SINR (right) for TN UE with different receiver configurations. Here, no isolation distance is considered, i.e., $D_{iso} = 0$ km; hence, it represents the worst-case scenario resulting in maximum interference. Fig. 4(a) illustrates the interference reduction capabilities of the receiver schemes under consideration. The allowed interference level is set at -5 dB INR, consistent with similar interference protection criteria, as given by ITU-R M.2292 for IMT-Advanced systems [17]. As expected, the single-antenna case exhibits the highest INR levels, indicating the poorest performance due to its susceptibility to interference. The MRC design shows a modest improvement of 2-3 dB in the median INR, which aligns with expectations since MRC primarily focuses on enhancing SNR rather than mitigating interference. Notably, MRC can occasionally perform worse than the single-antenna scenario shown in the upper tail of the distribution, likely because MRC, being unaware of the interference direction and operating in NLOS, might inadvertently amplify the interfering signals by directing the beam towards interfering nodes. In contrast, IRC demonstrates significant improvements in INR for the entire distribution. Specifically, the 4×4 and 16×16 IRC configurations show improvements in the median of 10 dB and 25 dB, respectively, compared to the single-antenna case. These results indicate that IRC is the most effective technique for interference reduction, as expected. Moreover,

Fig. 4. The CDF of INR and SINR for TN UE with different receiver settings.

Fig. 5. Median INR versus isolation distance.

only the 16×16 antenna with IRC meets our coexistence criterion of -5 dB INR, although it still yields higher INR values in 13-14% of the distribution (upper tail). This tail can be explained by instances where the angles of the interference and desired signal align with each other. Fig. 4(b) presents a different perspective on performance when evaluating SINR. Here, the impact of MRC designs becomes more evident, as they significantly enhance SINR levels for TN UEs and consistently outperform a single antenna UEs. This means that unintended interference amplification observed in Fig. 4(a) does not degrade overall signal quality. Nonetheless, the IRC 16×16 configuration continues to yield the best performance values. The difference between MRC and IRC observed for SINR (4-8 dB) not being as pronounced as for INR (10-20 dB) suggests that MRC may also be a viable option due to its simpler implementation.

We will now focus on the results with varying D_{iso} . Fig. 5 illustrates the median INR (interference level) relative to

the isolation distance, D_{iso} . The allowed interference level is set again at -5 dB INR. In general, increasing the isolation distance between NTN and TN cells reduces the INR level, because the satellite antenna's beam is more tightly focused on the NTN cell, causing interference with the TN primarily through its side lobes, which have lower antenna gain as the isolation distance increases (see Fig. 3). As expected, the highest interference levels occur with the single-antenna configuration, which can only coexist with an NTN at an isolation distance of approximately 300 km. However, by applying MRC with 4×4 and 16×16 UPA configurations, the required D_{iso} decreases to 240 km and 180 km, respectively. Further reduction of the isolation distance to 100 km is achievable with a 4×4 UPA using IRC. Most notably, with a 16×16 UPA and IRC, the INR remains below the allowed threshold even when the NTN and TN cells overlap (i.e., $D_{iso} = 0$ km). It is worth noting that this curve does not follow a similar pattern as the others. This is because the 16×16 UPA with IRC cancels interference so effectively that it is limited only by the noise level, leading to saturation. As a result, we observe only minor fluctuations in the range of ± 1 dB. This result may suggest that with a 16×16 UPA using IRC, an isolation distance may not be necessary. However, it is important to recall that these results are based on median INR. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the 16×16 UPA with IRC exhibits a broader upper tail that deviates from the median value by more than 10 dB, indicating that an isolation distance may overall still be required.

Fig. 6 illustrates the median performance improvement in terms of SINR versus isolation distance, D_{iso} . The reference point is the worst performance value, corresponding to a single-antenna receiver with $D_{iso} = 0$ km, meaning the curves show SINR improvement in dB relative to this baseline. As expected, the SINR level increases with greater isolation distance. For the single-antenna case, SINR improvement ranges from 0 to 9 dB over an isolation distance of 0 to 300

Fig. 6. Median SINR improvement versus isolation distance.

km. In addition, multi-antenna receivers significantly enhance SINR. Specifically, the 4×4 UPA with MRC/IRC achieves a 15-25 dB improvement, while the 16×16 UPA yields a 28-36 dB enhancement. Moreover, for the 16×16 UPA with IRC, the improvement slope remains steady, indicating that with sufficient antenna size, IRC can effectively mitigate interference and is limited only by the noise level. Meanwhile, MRC curves have a similar slope as single-antenna, because MRC basically amplifies the desired signal only. While IRC generally outperforms MRC, the SINR difference between them is not as pronounced as in the INR case shown in Fig. 5. Notably, the gap between IRC and MRC is more apparent in scenarios with strong interference (shorter isolation distances), but it diminishes as the isolation distance increases, i.e., when there is less interference. This demonstrates that IRC is the preferable choice in cases of strong interference, while MRC might be sufficient in all other cases. This result also suggests that SINR may be a more appropriate performance metric for coexistence studies involving multi-antenna receiver techniques, despite INR being the standard measure typically used in this context.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has explored the use of linear multi-antenna receiver techniques at TN UEs, specifically MRC and IRC, to enhance the coexistence of NTN and TNs during downlink communication in the upper mid-band spectrum by mitigating interference and improving the signal quality at TN UEs. The simulation results demonstrated that while MRC offers modest improvements in INR, IRC is far more effective in reducing interference, particularly in scenarios involving larger antenna arrays. Notably, the IRC technique with a 16×16 UPA configuration minimizes the isolation distance, allowing NTN and TN cells to overlap in the majority of the cases. This finding underscores IRC's potential as a vital tool for enabling seamless NTN-TN integration in FR3. However, the close performance of MRC in SINR enhancement, coupled

with its lower implementation complexity, suggests that MRC may also be a viable option for scenarios where simplicity is critical, and interference is not too severe, particularly at larger isolation distance. The findings highlight the importance of carefully selecting multi-antenna receiver schemes and antenna configurations for enabling NTN/TN coexistence in FR3 for future radio.

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